

to foliage feeders. Seventy-two accessions of 13 wild species, one *O. sativa*/*O. nivara* hybrid, and an unknown *Oryza* sp. were resistant or

moderately resistant to leafhoppers and planthoppers. Thirteen accessions of eight wild species were resistant to multiple pests (Table 2). □

Resistance in different rice genetic lines to rice moth *Sitotroga cerealella* (Oliv.)

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We tested resistance in various rice lines in Pakistan to rice moth *S. cerealella* (Oliv.), an important storage pest of rice, wheat, and maize.

Rice moth was reared in the laboratory at 28 ± 3 °C and $63 \pm 4\%$ relative humidity. Rice grain also was conditioned at this temperature for a week. About 100 24-h-old eggs of the rice moth were placed on 30 g of conditioned grain. Larvae hatched and were allowed to complete their life cycle. Adult moths started emerging 25 d after infestation.

Infested grain was sieved through No. 20 mesh to separate the frass and food remains, weighed, and loss calculated. Total grains and number of damaged grains were counted and percent damaged grains calculated. The experiment was replicated three times. Moisture content of test lines ranged between 11.1 and 12.6%.

Genetic line 1017-6-B and OP62 showed significantly less grain loss (see table). Highest susceptibility was in line 4439 and Bas 385.

Grain weight was investigated as a possible source of resistance, but no relationship could be detected. Correlations between 1,000-grain weight and weight loss ($r = -0.32$), damaged grains ($r = -0.26$), and number of adults that emerged ($r = -0.31$) were negative. □

Dry weight loss, damaged grains, and number of *S. cerealella* adults that emerged in storage of different rice genetic lines of Pakistan.^a

Genetic line	Crown at ^b	Dry weight loss (%)	Damaged grains (%)	Adults (no.)
1017-6-B	NARC	0.3 a	0.2 a	5 a
OP62	KK	0.7 a	0.8 a	13 ab
OP61	KK	1.0 ab	1.2 bc	24 bc
IET4094	KK	1.2 ab	1.2 bc	27 cd
IR64	KK	2.1 bc	1.5 bcd	38 c-f
TN1	NIAB	2.3 bc	1.7 cde	34 c-f
DM24	NIAB	2.4 bc	1.8 c-f	40 def
OP57	KK	2.7 cd	1.99 c-f	47 efg
DM38	NIAB	2.9 cd	1.9 c-g	49 fg
OP53	KK	2.9 cd	2.0 c-g	51 fgh
OP54	KK	3.2 cde	2.2 d-h	60 ghi
DM25	NIAB	3.3 cde	2.3 e-h	63 hij
DM28	NIAB	3.5 d-g	2.4 e-h	64 hij
1021-6	NARC	4.0 def	2.7 ghi	65 hij
IR2053	KK	4.3 efg	2.8 hi	68 ijk
1053-1-2 (94)	NARC	4.8 fg	2.9 hi	68 ijk
1021-5	NARC	5.6 gh	2.5 fgh	67 ijk
4048-3	NARC	6.2 h	3.3 ij	72 ijk
50189-8-6	NARC	6.4 h	3.7 j	75 jkl
Bas 385A	NARC	6.5 h	3.7 jk	75 jkl
KS282	KK	6.9 h	4.7 l	78 lm
Bas 385	NIAB	8.4 i	5.2 l	81 lm
4439	NARC	8.8 i	5.5 l	91 m

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter do not differ significantly from each other at the 5% level. ^b KK = Kala Shah Kaku; NARC = National Agricultural Research Centre, Islamabad; NIAB = Nuclear Institute of Agricultural Biology, Faisalabad.

Excess water tolerance

Tolerance of rainfed lowland rice cultivars and breeding lines for submergence at seedling stage

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Submergence tolerance is a major trait needed for rice grown in submergence-prone rainfed lowland or tidal wetlands. Native rice cultivars (FR13A, FR43B) have been identified with 12 d submergence tolerance. Other cultivars (Chenab 64-117) have about 7 d submergence tolerance. But those cultivars have low yield potential. New donors and recombinant lines for improved plant type background are needed.

We screened 55 rainfed lowland rices (traditional cultivars and improved lines) in the greenhouse for tolerance for complete submergence. Seedlings were raised in 40- × 25- × 6-cm porcelain trays filled with Maahas clay soil. Ten lines, at 10 seedlings/line were maintained in each tray in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

Seedlings were completely submerged 10 d after seeding (DAS) in a 150- × 150- × 45-cm artificial tank. Water depth 30 cm above the soil level, water temperature 30 °C, and light intensity 0.59 watt/m² were maintained, FR13A and IR42 were used as resistant and susceptible checks. Seedling height was measured before submergence (H_1) and after 7 d submergence (H_2). Survival was measured 5 d after the end of submergence (22 DAS). Elongation was calculated as $H_2 - H_1$ for entries with at least 20% survival.

Survival of IR43522-37-3-3 and IR40931-33-1-3-2 compared with that of resistant check FR13A (see table). Ten other lines were moderately resistant (at least 40% survival).